

Supplementary Table 1. Diet composition

Diets	Linoleic Acid (LA)	
	1%	22.5%
kcal/g	4.7	4.7
Oils (g)	202.5	202.5
Coconut oil	133	21.5
Flaxseed oil	10	10
Lard	0	0
Safflower oil	0	45
Soybean oil	2	2
Sunflower oil	57.5	124
Carbohydrate (g)	255.6	255.6
Protein (g)	203	203
% energy from carbohydrate	31	31
% energy from protein	24	24
% energy from fat	45	45
% from SFA	31	8
% from LA	1	22.5
Fatty acids (g)	199.8	199.6
C6, Caproic	0.8	0.1
C8, Caprylic	10.2	1.7
C10, Capric	7.8	1.3
C12, Lauric	63.3	10.2
C14, Myristic	23.9	3.9
C16, Palmitic	14	11.9
C16:1, Palmitoleic	0	0
C18, Stearic	16.9	7.4
C18:1, Oleic	52.4	55.8
C18:2, Linoleic	4.7	101.4
C18:3, Linolenic	5.8	5.9
C20:4, Arachidonic	0	0
C20:5, Eicosapentaenoic	0	0
C22:6, Docosahexaenoic	0	0
SFA (%)	69	18.3
MUFA (%)	26	28
PUFA (%)	5	53.7

Supplementary Table 2. Primers for qPCR

Primer sequences for liver, gonadal white adipose tissue and hypothalamus qPCR			
Gene Name	Forward Primer	Reverse Primer	Accession #
Pomc	GGAAGATGCCGAGATTCTGC	TCCGTTGCCAGGAAACAC	NM_008895
Cart	GCTCAAGAGTAAACGCATTCC	GTCCCTTACAAGCACTTCAA	NM_013732
Npy	ACTGACCCTCGCTCTATCTC	TCTCAGGGCTGGATCTCTTG	NM_023456
Agrp	CTCCACTGAAGGGCATCAGAA	ATCTAGCACCTCCGCCAAA	NM_007427.2
Lepr	AGAATGACGCAGGGCTGTAT	TCCTTGTGCCCAGGAACAAT	NM_146146.2
Ghsr	CAGGGACCAGAACCACAAAC	AGCCAGGCTCGAAAGACT	NM_177330
Insr	GTGTTCCGGAACCTGATGAC	GTGATACCAGAGCATAGGAG	NM_010568
Glp1r	TTCAAGCTGTATCTGAGCATAG	AGATGACACGGATGAAGATAAG	NM_021332
Pparg	CTGCTCAAGTATGGTGTCCATGAG	GAGGAACTCCCTGGTCATGAATC	NM_011146.3
Esr1	GCGCAAGTGTTACGAAGTG	TTCGGCCTTCCAAGTCATC	NM_007956
Esr2	AATGTCCACCCGCTAGGCATTC	CTCCATGTCTTGCGTAGGTCTC	NM_010157
Foxo1	CAATGGCTATGGTAGGATGG	TTTAAATGTAGCCTGCTCAC	NM_019739
Pepck	AGCGGATATGGTGGGAAC	GGTCTCCACTCCTTGTTT	NM_011044.2
G6pc	GCCTCCTGTCGGATACAGAA	TGCACCGCAAGAGCATT	NM_008061.4
Fasn	GGGTTCTAGCCAGCAGAGTC	TCAGCCACTTGAGTGTCTC	NM_007988.3
Acly	GTCAGCCAAGGCAATTCAGAG	TAACCCGGCATACTTGAACC	NM_134037.3
Acc1	GCCATTGGTATTGGGGCTTAC	CCCGACCAAGGACTTTGTTG	NM_133360.2
Acc2	TGTCCCAGGAGGCTGCATTGA	TGTGCAGGTCCAGTTTCTTGTGT	NM_133904.2
Dgat2	ACTCTGGAGGTTGGCACCAT	GGGTGTGGCTCAGGAGGAT	NM_026384.3
Fatp2	TTCGGGAACACAGGTCTTC	CAAGGCCTGTCCCATACCAT	NM_011978.2
Fatp5	CGTACATTCGCAACAAGTTTCC	TCGAAAGAACCAACCCTTCT	NM_009512.2
Ppara	TCGAAAAAGAAGTCCCATACACAA	TCGAAAAAGAAGTCCCATACACAA	NM_008904.2
Srebp1c	TTGATAGAAGACCGGTAGCGC	TTGATAGAAGACCGGTAGCGC	NM_011480.3
Pgc1a	TCGAAAAAGAAGTCCCATACACAA	TCGAAAAAGAAGTCCCATACACAA	NM_008904.2
Gapdh	TGACGTGCCGCTGGAGAAA	AGTGTAGCCCAAGATGCCCTTCAG	NM_008084.2
Hprt	GCAGTACAGCCCCAAAATGG	AACAAAGTCTGGCCTGTATCCA	NM_013556
Actb	GCCCTGAGGCTCTTTTCCA	TAGTTTCATGGATGCCACAGGA	NM_007393.3

Supplementary Table 3. Primers for qPCR

Taqman assays for ileum qPCR		
Gene name	Protein	Assay ID
<i>Il6</i>	IL6	Mm00446190_m1
<i>Tnf</i>	TNF α	Mm00443258_m1
<i>Nos2</i>	iNOS	Mm00440502_m1
<i>Ocln</i>	occludin	Mm00500912_m1
<i>Tjp1</i>	ZO-1	Mm01320638_m1
<i>Gcg</i>	preproglucagon	Mm00801714_m1
<i>Pcsk1</i>	prohormone convertase 1/3 (PC1/3)	Mm00479023_m1
<i>Slc5a1</i>	SGLT1	Mm00451203_m1
<i>Slc2a2</i>	GLUT2	Mm00480431_m1
<i>Fiaf</i>	FIAF	Mm00446229_m1
<i>Hmbs</i>	HMBS	Mm01143545_m1

Supplementary Figure 1. AUC of cumulative weight gain and food intake. Data are presented as mean \pm SD. Differences were determined by two-way ANOVA followed with Holm-Sidak post-hoc comparison between and within genotype groups (* $p < 0.05$). Significantly different results of ANOVA test were: (A) genotype $F(1,38)=10.62$, $p=0.0024$; (C) genotype $F(1,17)=12.83$, $p=0.0023$.

Supplementary Figure 2. Hemodynamic measurements. Data are presented as mean \pm SD. Differences were determined by three-way ANOVA followed with Holm-Sidak post-hoc comparison between and within treatment groups. Significantly different results of ANOVA test were: Systolic blood pressure diet: $F(1,63)=5.097$, $p=0.0274$; Diastolic blood pressure: diet $F(1,63)=4.296$, $p=0.0423$; Heart rate: genotype \times treatment $F(1,63)=9.927$, $p=0.0025$.

Supplementary Figure 3. Colonic histology. **(A)** H&E staining of colon tissues to visualize morphology and **(B)** AB-PAS staining to detect mucin-producing goblet cells. **(C)** Detection of colonic COX-2 by immunohistochemistry. Sample sizes were 6 for each group.

Supplementary Figure 4. Ileal qPCR. Data are presented as mean ± SD. Differences were determined by three-way ANOVA followed with Holm-Sidak post-hoc comparison (* p < 0.05) between and within treatment groups. Significant ANOVA results are shown under graph.

Supplementary Figure 5. Diversity metrics of fecal microbial communities. (A) Alpha diversity metrics showing differences for Pielou's evenness, Shannon index, Faith's phylogenetic diversity (Faith PD) and observed ASVs. Significant difference between groups was determined by Kruskal-Wallis test followed by the two-stage step-up method of Benjamini, Krieger and Yekutieli with FDR adjusted p value, $q<0.05$. Same letter indicates no difference. (B) Beta diversity dissimilarity metrics (weighted unifracs, Jaccard, Bray Curtis and unweighted unifracs) are shown as 2D-principal coordinate analysis (PCoA) plots. Analysis of variance was determined using ADONIS and 10,000X permutation analysis in the vegan package within R Studio v.4.1.2 (R Studio Software, Boston, MA, USA). The r^2 and p values for diet and treatment effects are shown.

□ WT-Veh-1% ○ WT-Veh-22.5% □ *fat-1*-Veh-1% ○ *fat-1*-Veh-22.5%
■ WT-EB-1% ● WT-EB-22.5% ■ *fat-1*-EB-1% ● *fat-1*-EB-22.5%

Supplementary Figure 6. mRNA expression level of *Esr2* in the hypothalamic tissue. Data are presented as mean \pm SD. Differences were determined by three-way ANOVA followed with Holm-Sidak post-hoc comparison between and within treatment groups. Significant ANOVA results ($p < 0.05$) are shown under graph.

□ WT-Veh-1% ○ WT-Veh-22.5% □ *fat-1*-Veh-1% ○ *fat-1*-Veh-22.5%
■ WT-EB-1% ● WT-EB-22.5% ■ *fat-1*-EB-1% ● *fat-1*-EB-22.5%

Supplementary Figure 7. mRNA expression level of *Srebp1c* in the liver. Data are presented as mean \pm SD. Differences were determined by three-way ANOVA followed with Holm-Sidak post-hoc comparison between and within treatment groups. Significant ANOVA results ($p < 0.05$) are shown under graph.

Supplementary Figure 8. Gonadal white adipose tissue qPCR of lipid metabolism markers. Data are presented as mean \pm SD. Differences were determined by three-way ANOVA followed with Holm-Sidak post-hoc comparison (* $p < 0.05$) between and within treatment groups. Significant ANOVA results are shown under graph.